

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: Jovihyo****FIRST NAME: Vincent****PROGRAM CODE: DMCR****COURSE CODE : ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 1****INSTRUCTOR: Prof. Cleenewerck**

Edit or delete text to show actual information below:

The author applied UK conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics.

The author used Turabian (in-text/parenthetical)

The author did *not* use Zotero to insert referencesThe author did *not* use Grammarly Premium (EUCLID provides access)

The author used the following software: (e.g., MSWord on Windows 10)

STANDARD ACADEMIC WRITING

1) INTRODUCTION

I have just embarked on a doctorate degree journey at Euclid University. The programme involves greater commitments and academic writing that will march the standard of any graduate work anywhere. The standards set out by the university for standard academic writing cannot be compromised. As an adult learner, I am ready to follow up every guideline provided to move forward in my chosen career. The materials have been carefully compiled to educate both old and new writers to adhere to the norms of writing academic papers at graduate level. Herein, the standpoint is that all ingredients associated with comprehensive and readable works are in place. This course also reminds me of my secondary school days when we used to battle with part of speech to correctly express ourselves in English. As one who is hoping of being a mediator to conflict parties, good communication is fundamental to any successful dialogue. Also, all assignments must be written by me, in my words and ideas.

2) THE COURSE PACK FOR PERIOD 1

The course pack for period one compiled by Euclid University dwells on the basics of writing a good essay. It is a prerequisite for any writer to express his or her ideas vividly to capture the imagination of readers. The taste of food makes people to eat it and not how big or nice it may appear on the surface. The “Essay Writing, The Basics” provides hints on essay writing that author shall start early, read, research and think as much as possible (EUCLID 2015, 2).

The course pack explains the template for all works at EUCLID and warns against plagiarism and its consequences (EUCLID 2015, 13) especially with academic works at Euclid University. That means all borrowed quotations and paraphrases must be properly cited (EUCLID 2015, 13). The rules of writing an excellent paper are also spelt out clearly starting from the main thesis and staying focused as well as writing clearly amongst others (EUCLID 2015, 43).

Some of the differences in American and British English highlighted and the recommended American English and Chicago Manual of Style but other on the template can be used as well (EUCLID 2015, 52 & 54). The course pack's "CMS CRIB SHEET" gives details on Chicago style and usage and closed with some Latin words (EUCLID 2015, 66).

The course pack gives an insight of the introductory part of the writing, the body outlining details of the topic and drawing conclusion as well as referencing (EUCLID 2015, 2). The arrangement of the documents makes it easier for planning and writing research papers bearing in mind that it is one's own ideas that drives the writing and not copying and pasting other people's works without acknowledging them. However, citations, quotations and references to other writers' works are integral part of any academic writing but the excessive use may lead to losing your original works or worse still termed plagiarism.. These should be used only and where necessary to support one's original work. They should be used only if where they will help explain one's perception of the topic clearer or where one's own explanation will connect such work. In writing academic works, it is mandatory to use the templates provided to write all your response, quiz, major and dissertation papers. The course pack distinguishes between American and British English to which a student must decide which one to follow. The advice here is that whichever a student decides; he or she must use that choice consistently bearing in mind the variations in punctuations and spellings as well as the pronunciations when speaking (EUCLID 2015, 54).

I have always played with the words "its'" and "it's", "your" and "you're" without looking deep in what each stands for. In my study of the pack, I became fascinated by the short but exclusive meanings to these words (EUCLID 2015, 48). "It's" stands for "it is". For example, "it's" a great day, "its" is the possessive form of it and can be used as "The bird made its' nest". It is appropriate to understand and use these words accordingly so that proper meanings can be curved out of them. The "your" connotes a possessive form meaning the way you look and your possessions, for example, "your" stomach is very big or "your" car is nice. The "you're" demonstrates an action as "you're" going to fail the examination. The grammatical expressions have varying meanings and can be confused when not properly used. The issue of "I" and "Me" poses a question in our everyday spoken English as we transpose one for the other. "I" and "me" (EUCLID 2015, 51). "I" simply is an action word that commends. For example, "I" want you to water the flowers or "I" want to go to the toilet. While "me" is at the receiving end, for example, the lecturer came to "me" or better still, he questioned "me" over my failure to submit the response paper on time.

Plagiarism has been mentioned many times in the course pack showing that pretence in academic writing is a crime. If you want to write, conceive your ideas, plan the ideas logically and dwell on them diligently in your own way. Quotations and paraphrases are all tools of writing any paper hence no one can come up with something entirely new. However, while tapping others' ideas, we should give the credit they deserve and show that our new ideas have been developed in agreement or disagreement with theirs. A good writer should be able to cite one or few citations but not to depend solely on citations to build up his or her work. Citation becomes obvious where one needs to clarify a point and link the point to previous work from another writer. Where there is citation in any work, there should be acknowledgement given to the author or authors clearly to avoid the axe of plagiarism (EUCLID 2015, 13).

At Euclid University, academic writing calls for the writer to adhere to the principle of adopting one form of writing and consistently applying it throughout the response paper, quiz paper, major paper or dissertation. The consistency is a guide which makes one's style of writing admirably and understandable by his or her readers. The writer should focus on the project, be it technical, commercial or business and use the writing so that the target audience will be able to understand the familiar words and style used. This is because many authors address issues in a variety of styles, mixing up technical, business and commercial in one project that is supposed to have its own language and style. Euclid University recommends the Chicago rules (Turabian) and American English as standards for writing academic papers. However, other international rules are acceptable and if consistently used will serve the purpose as well (EUCLID 2015, 52).

American and British English are main language styles used in standard academic writing at Euclid University. There are differences in spellings, punctuations and other ways. However, in academic writing, the author must use one form so that readers keep reading and pronouncing the article in that way. The differences are either in pronunciation, spelling or even meaning. Examples are "advertisement (advert, ad)" are spelt same but pronounced differently; "Axe and ax." or "colour and color" are spelt differently but pronounced same (ECULID 2015, 54). There are many differences in the two styles of using English in writing academic papers and one must be mindful of choosing one, either American or British and consistently applying the features therein. Furthermore, whether as native speakers or not, emphasis must be laid on which choice that suits the writer most hence the alternative. The conceptual issue here at EUCLID, is which one of these two concepts will address your writing style that will put you in a consistent mode with your audience.

3) CONCLUSION

In my career as an accountant and economist for the past four decades, I have come to realise the importance of creative writing as a tool of getting attention from your audience. In academic writing, the star audience is your course lecturer and others that have interest in your work. The writing must be of the standard required of academic style implored and persuasive enough to attract the attention of your would-be readers.

Euclid University has compiled this course pack carefully to accommodate research beginners and even for the experienced ones. The university has done its job by providing a comprehensive course pack to enhance the techniques of producing an academic document that stand the test of modern time and academics.

Therefore, it is my outmost belief that the course documents provided are symbolic and have enriched me with the most ignored part of speech that without going through the pack, I would still be making such errors in my writing and speeches. The task must be done, and I am prepared to advance in my academic writing that will pave way for the successful completion of my Doctorate in Mediation and Conflict Resolution (DMCR) at Euclid University.

WORK CITED

EUCLID. 2015. *ACA-401 Coursepack*. Washington DC: Euclid UniversityPress. <https://eucliduniversity.net/periods/aca-401d-period-1/> (accessed July 29, 2019).

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. *ACA-401/ACA 401D Course Pack: Period 1*. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.